

Using Foundation Model Embeddings to Map Colorado's Built Hazard Interface for Wildfire

Aleksander Berg ^{a,b,*} and Stefan Leyk ^{a,b}

^a *University of Colorado Boulder Department of Geography, Aleksander Berg – aleksander.berg@colorado.edu, Stefan Leyk - stefan.leyk@colorado.edu*

^b *University of Colorado Boulder Institute of Behavioral Science*

* Corresponding author

Abstract:

Since 1980, the United States alone has seen 403 “billion dollar” weather and climate related disasters, accounting for 16,918 deaths and over \$2.9 trillion dollars in damages. In the past three years, the U.S. has seen 73 of these billion-dollar disasters with 1,534 total deaths and \$461.6 billion in damages. Climate and weather hazards such as fire, landslides, floods, heat waves, and cold snaps are accelerating in their destructiveness and deadliness due to climate change, development patterns, differential vulnerability, and numerous other human-environmental factors. In this project we propose a new framework and methodology for dynamically mapping spaces where the built environment and hazard prone areas meet, which we term the Built Hazard Interface or BHI. We use the Clay geospatial foundation model to generate embeddings of Landsat imagery to build a semantic picture of land cover in our study area. We use these embeddings in concert with the highest resolution data available on the built environment (parcel and building footprint data) in a LightGBM classifier to map Colorado’s BHI for wildland fire. We present a testbed analysis generating these maps for the wildland urban interface (WUI), a space interaction between flammable vegetation and the built environment, for the state of Colorado in 2010-2020. Our workflow using a foundational geospatial model presents a start on how to map hazard prone spaces in a way that better represents the complex climatological, environmental, and social processes that drive heightened exposure in the first place at the spatial and temporal scales at which they operate.